

Insights on Teaching Genre Writing: Moroccan EFL University Professors' Perspectives

Abderrazzak Belbouah

Faculty of Languages, Letters and Arts, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco

Mounir Chibi

Faculty of Languages, Letters and Arts, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco

Abstract

The current study explored the implementation of genre writing pedagogy in teaching EFL writing at Moroccan universities. Its focus was on how Moroccan university professors perceive the integration of genre writing in improving the writing skills of Moroccan Master students in the different EFL departments. For such an end, the study adopted a qualitative content analysis whose instrument was a semi-structured interview with Moroccan EFL university professors (N=16). The main findings indicated a strong recognition of the value of genre writing in developing students' academic and communicative skills. They also recognized challenges related to students' familiarity with genre conventions and highlighted the growing role of technology in supporting instruction. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for a well-integrated and technologically supported integration of genre-based writing instruction in Moroccan higher education.

Keywords: *Genre Writing, EFL departments, Morocco, professors' perceptions.*

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Introduction

Academic success at university depends largely on the quality of students' writing. Regardless of their education level or disciplinary focus, students have to produce high-quality written texts to meet the requirements of their courses. English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students are no exception. More importantly, the need to master academic writing for EFL students extends beyond classroom requirements to encompass their future academic and professional pursuits. In fact, EFL university graduates will most likely be required to produce quality written texts as researchers, academics, or employees in professional contexts where effective writing is essential.

Of equal importance is the need for students to be aware of the writing conventions adopted by the academic communities to which they belong. To be effective writers, students must not only write well but also use, for instance, the lexico-grammatical, rhetorical, and discursal features that are common—or at least preferred—within

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their disciplines. Consequently, writing curricula should be designed with attention to the features that distinguish writing in one discipline from another. The goal, therefore, is to help students develop their writing skills with a focus on the conventions specific to their field of study. This is the core concern of genre writing (GW), which studies and identifies the writing features specific to different writing communities. The identification of these features provides members of a writing community the guidance they need to produce texts reflecting their community's writing identity.

Because every writing community has its own writing identity, teaching students to write with maximum respect for what defines that identity is indispensable. Accordingly, EFL curricula need to be tailored to meet the writing needs of the specific. As such, science students should learn how scientists write, literature students need training in how literary scholars write, and applied linguistics students should be taught to write in accordance with the conventions of applied linguistics.

The current study builds on this premise to explore the perspectives Moroccan EFL university professors advocate with regards to teaching writing within a GW perspective. It is, however, students in applied linguistics departments that the study focuses on. For such an end, the questions the study tries to answer are:

1. How do Moroccan university EFL professors perceive the role of genre-based pedagogy in developing students' academic writing skills in applied linguistics?
2. What challenges and strategies do these professors identify in implementing genre writing instruction within the EFL curriculum at Moroccan universities?

Literature Review

Genre Writing Approach

In his article "History and Genre," Ralph Cohen (1986) outlines the fundamental aspects necessary for understanding the concept of genre in its broad sense. Firstly, he notes that 'genre' is a term introduced to replace the 19th-century terminology of 'kinds' and 'species,' which refer to both classes and individuals. Secondly, Cohen defines genre as any grouping of works characterized by shared similarities. Thirdly, he emphasizes that genres are flexible categories, with each work within a genre potentially altering it through additions, contradictions, or changes, particularly in relation to closely related works. Finally, Cohen highlights that texts can belong to multiple genres and serve diverse generic purposes.

However, situating genre within the linguistic and semantic borders of a certain definition is challenged in the literature. One of these challenges is charged by Michel Foucault (1972), who highlights the difficulty to classify texts as belonging to one grouping when in the first place they are written, shared, and devised differently. Jack Derrida, as quoted by Cohen (1972), hypothesizes "any generic classification system is untenable because individual texts resist classification (...) because they are interpretatively indeterminate" (p.204). In support of this criticism, Benoit (2000) contends genre theory is limited in its assumption that one predominant factor (frequently, though not solely, the context) can play a crucial role in shaping and clarifying the making of a particular rhetorical genre. Last but not least, Stam (2000) wonders:

"Are genres really 'out there' in the world, or are they merely the constructions of analysts?"

Is there a finite taxonomy of genres or are they in principle infinite? Are genres timeless

Platonic essences or ephemeral, time-bound entities? Are genres culture-bound or transcultural?... Should genre analysis be descriptive or proscriptive?" (p. 14)

The criticism the questions hereabove uphold against the possibility of classifying, for instance, films, poems, and novels under the umbrella of a certain genre is weakened by the enormous amount of EFL literature that supports the use of the term genre to classify written texts.

Of these is the definition of Carolyn Miller that genre is any "typified rhetorical action based in recurrent situations" (Miller, 1984, p.159), and learning it equip individuals with the power necessary for them to effectively act in their social community (p.165). Miller does not only confirm the possibility to group texts and other documents under a specific genre but also highlights the importance of the community members to learn about it. With regards to EFL writing, genre classification can help researchers study writing, teachers to teach it, and learners to learn it. Thence, there stands the genre-based approach as an important component in the teaching and learning of EFL writing.

However, it is of special importance to highlight how some researchers argue against the categorization of a text within a genre and not within any other. For instance, a text needs not "be categorized singularly, as either tragedy or comedy, for example, or simply, as genre writing, such as mysteries, romances, science fiction;" consequently, genres can be described through what they are as well as by what they are not because "every work involves more than one genre, even if only implicitly" (Devitt, 2000, p. 701). It is pertinent to the discussion to assert that genres encompass any communicative occurrences distinguished by their communicative intentions and various patterns of organization, expression, content, and target audience (Hyon, 1996; Swales, 1990).

The GW approach departs from the claim that considers genre "a culturally recognized message type with a conventional internal structure, such as an affidavit, a biology research article, or a business memo" (Biber, 2006, p. 11). It is also a "cognitive and cultural concept," which is defined "as the abstract, goal-oriented, staged and socially recognized ways of using language delimited by communicative purposes, performed social (inter)actions within rhetorical contexts, and formal properties" (Cheng, 2006, p. 77). Hyland (2008a; 2008b) notes genre is a term to group texts together in order to represent the features that are common and shared in and by community that writes them.

Similarly, Swales (1990, p. 58) notes genre is "a class of communicative events, the members of which share some set of communicative purposes," and which they learn by recognizing and understanding the language features and patterns they encounter in the texts they read (L. Price & J. Price, 2002). In this sense, genre "offers a comprehensive model of languages in use...describes how our language choices will differ depending on certain aspects of context... And suggests a pedagogy that looks outward to the social dimension of learning" (Derewianka, 2015, p. 11).

The assertions above connote GW considers what learners, as members of a writing community, need to know in order to effectively fit within the writing of the social communities wherein they make part of. Fitting means being aware and able to write in a way that abides by the rhetorical and formal writing norms, and towards the

communicative purposes established by these writing communities. It is a fact, for instance, that “academic writing is always situated, and it is not merely a tool but a complex social action to how a disciplinary community produces knowledge” (Goldschmidt, 2014, p. 25). ‘How’ can, as Hyland (2003) proclaims, refer to acts of requesting, describing, reporting, and, in general, getting things done. Accordingly, it is these needs and how to achieve them that writing genre curricula target in EFL classes because without them, students cannot “produce a composition to be successfully accepted by a particular English-language discourse community” (Tuan, 2011, p. 123).

However, it is worth to mention that writers within the same community write with their individualized writing identity, or unique writing point – similar to the term unique selling point that is used in business to distinguish a product from others in the market. This is because “philosophically, rhetorically, and linguistically, no two instances of genre can be identical, but they can still share genre” and that “the unique language-user at a unique moment encounters a particular task in a distinct community setting” (Devitt, 2015, p. 11). Difference and similarity (Miller, 1984) as well as uniqueness and dialogism (Bakhtin, 1986) are key features of texts written within one genre community. Of equal importance is the idea that “genres and their conventions are not fixed, but continually reinvented by individuals and groups” (Rose, 2003, p. 25).

Genre Writing Learning

Understanding GW requires viewing it, not only from the perspectives of a teaching stand, but also from the angles of its learning components. This is because GW places learners in the center of the pedagogical endeavor it promotes for effective writing lessons. However, theorists focus more on the needs of the learners and the development of teaching material than on the learning processes and the learners (Cheng, 2006). Cheng also notes, “there is inadequate documentation of the processes or the contexts of learning in” studies about GW (p.79).

Cheng (2006) highlighted a few topics researchers should explore to study GW from a learner’s stand. Of these is learners’ motivation. The focus is on the extent to which students are more motivated to learn how to write in GW classes than students in classes using other writing approaches, namely product and process writing. Cheng also emphasizes the need for deep investigative research about the insights and reflections of learners with regards to the GW classes they attend. Last but not least, Cheng claims the lack of the understanding of “the full intricacies of being a learner” (p. 80) is worth to investigate by GW theorists and practitioners. Worth to mention is that the current study addresses GW from the perspectives of both learners and instructors.

Genre Writing Teaching

A genre-based writing lesson unfolds in two primary cycles. The first involves engaging students in classroom writing activities, while the second focuses on their independent writing (Feez, 1998). Within these two stages, four key sub-stages emerge in genre-based writing lessons: understanding the field, modeling and deconstructing the text, collaborative construction of the text, and independent construction and connecting related texts (Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Humphrey, 2017):

- Knowledge of field is the opening phase in a genre-based writing lesson. The aim of this stage is to build learners knowledge of the topic they will be writing about and to situate the field where it belongs. For such an end, “teachers and students

together discuss the background of the text to learn and share their experiences to deal with it” (Basthomi, 2020, p. 36). This is similar to the pre-learning activities used in language skill building and which are designed to stimulate learners’ schemata and enable them to envisage the rhetorical build-up and the linguistic characteristics of their community’s genre (Pan, 2008).

○ The modeling stage presents learners to as many model texts as possible with the goal of familiarizing them with the features of the writing genre they are learning. For instance, if the objective is to write an introduction of an applied linguistic paper, then learners will explore applied linguistics introductions through the deconstruction of the components that make them. The idea is that “through repetitive exposure to many materials pertaining to the target genre, students can get an idea about what makes a diary a diary, a book report a book report, a poem a poem or an explanatory essay an explanatory essay” (Lee, 2013, p. 318). Clearly thus is that within this phase, learners are provided with the input that is necessary for them to be metacognitively aware of the writing norms. They are consequently able to effectively produce texts which abide by the standards of the communities within which they write.

○ In the joint construction phase, teachers and learners together participate in the building of texts in the light of the discussions in the modeling stage. The collaborative production of texts at this level is guided towards the production of “a text that is of higher level than students could independently produce at that point in their development” (Dreyfus, 2013, p. 3). In other words, learners at this stage are supposed to have been aware of the writing conventions of their community target texts but are still unable to handle that on their own. This said means learners benefit from the opportunity “to construct their writing with their friends in a group and along the teacher’s guidance” (Hasanah et al., 2021, p. 210).

○ Independent construction is the final stage in a GW based lesson. Learners are supposed to have understood the rhetorical organization and the linguistic characteristics accepted by their writing community. Such understanding should be reflected by the learners’ ability to construct their own texts with the least scaffolding from their teachers. In addition, teachers promote “students’ capacity to relate the text with their reality and to make sense of the world around them” (Emilia, 2005). Learners at this level need to check the effectiveness of their texts by linking them to texts of writers in the same community and for the same social purpose.

Hammond et al. (1992) briefed the phases and modes of a GW writing lesson in the figure presented below:

Figure 1. Phases of a Genre Writing Lesson

The center of the lesson's focus is to upgrade the learners' ability to control the mechanisms necessary to produce written and/or spoken texts following four main phases: genre knowledge building, text modeling, collective construction of target texts, and individual production. Each stage of these aims "to achieve a different purpose, and so is associated with different types of classroom activities and teacher-learner roles" (Hyland, 2004, pp. 130–40).

Genre Writing Awareness (GWA)

Key to the teaching-learning of writing through the application of genre pedagogy is the building of learners' awareness of the writing conventions of the community they belong to. In other words, learners of engineering need to be aware of the type of writing commonly used by authors writing about engineering. GWA applies to all other walks of writing, including that relevant to the EFL context.

Awareness of the conventions of GW within a given writing community is explained and justified by metacognition theory, which relates to the awareness and self-regulation of a learner with regards to their thinking and the mental processes that occur during it (Flavell, 1979). While "awareness refers to knowledge of one's cognitive strengths and weakness, (...) self-regulation refers to coordinating one's awareness with appropriate action" (Wong, 1999). Differently said, awareness has to do with the learners knowing what they know and what they do not know about the writing patterns in the field of their specialty. Self-regulation, on the other hand, refers to the learners' ability to transfer their knowledge into texts that abide by the writing norms of their discipline. Awareness and self-regulation are analogous to what is commonly referred to in other research fields, such as in management, as the know-what and the know-how respectively.

The type of knowledge genre-based pedagogy targets in this sense and within this context is three-dimensional. One is declarative (knowing what things are). Another is procedural (knowing how things are done). The other is conditional (knowing why things are done) (Schraw et al., 2006). For instance, declarative knowledge might relate to students' knowledge of the structure of an abstract; procedural knowledge may do with their ability to know how to write sentences using the appropriate lexico-grammatical items; and conditional knowledge could relate to learners' ability to know the reasons for which they are engaged in the writing endeavor, and which of the two former levels of knowledge is in action. Then, it should be mentioned that the development of the three types of knowledge occurs holistically and interconnectedly, meaning the success to acquire one is inversely proportional to the success in acquiring the others (Azevedo & Alevén, 2013).

Self-regulation learning, on the other hand, is "the self-directive process by which learners transform their mental abilities into academic skills" in an environment that views learning in a "proactive way rather than as a covert event" wherein their roles are mostly reactive (Zimmerman, 2002). By being proactive, students share a significant part of the responsibility in cognitively and socially constructing their learning and that of their classmates. It is, in other words, "the process whereby students activate and sustain cognitions and behaviors systematically oriented towards the attainment of their learning goals" (Schunk, 2008, p. 465). These goals are in line with what educators understand as the target structures that language learners should master to write effectively.

Worth to mention is that genre awareness is not explicit teaching. Clark and Hernandez (2011) indicate explicit teaching of genre is limited to enabling students imitate how

texts in a particular genre are written; nevertheless, genre awareness qualifies them to gain insights on “how a given genre fulfills a rhetorical purpose and how the various components of a text, the writer, the intended reader, and the text itself, is informed by purpose” (pp. 66-67). In other words, while explicit teaching of a genre prepares learners to reproduce texts according to a writing genre, GWA deepens their understanding of the patterns, features, and variations relevant to it (p. 67).

Metacognition development is, henceforth, analogous to the case of a traveler – learner- who knows that they are travelling, how they are traveling, why they are traveling, and more importantly, they are in full control of their own means of traveling. Still, there is a guide – teacher- by their side and whose mission is to provide the necessary tools for this traveler to remain on the right path to reach the target destination.

Genre Writing Merits

Literature on the genre-based writing approach departs from and validates the claim that “writing varies with the social context in which it is produced” (Flowerdew, 1993, p. 307). Key to this claim is that lessons should be planned backwardly, and that is in the sense that the social needs of the learners are what set the starting point and the foci of the whole learning endeavor, and every planning follows accordingly. This claim also connotes different disciplines have different writing genres that learners should be aware of in order to produce texts that abide by the conventions agreed upon by the community in and for which they write. Also, the constructionist and collaborative negotiations of thought among learners and teachers during the phases of lessons is another chief constituent of genre-based writing, allowing students to actively engage in the learning process. Consequently, this approach, could be safely judged as being able to provide the learners with the sense of belonging they need to effectively operate as writers in their writing communities.

Hyland (2008b) describes genre-based writing pedagogy as “explicit”, “systematic,” “needs-based,” “supportive,” “empowering,” “critical,” and conscious raising,” and he adds “I am not claiming that all of these characteristics are unique to genre pedagogy, but I can think of no other approach which seeks to realize them all” (p.547). Considering these theoretical perspectives, which largely establish a solid foundation for GW pedagogy to effectively facilitate the teaching and learning of writing in general, and EFL writing in particular, Hyland (2018) identifies the following practical benefits of GW:

- Enabling learners from having a repertoire of information that they can use to write effectively within their community;
- Reminding students of the features they need for a textual organization that allows their readers to easily identify the purpose and meaning of the texts they write;
- Involving students in problem-solving activities;
- Raising students’ awareness of the lexico-grammatical and discursive features of their community’s genre;
- Scaffolding students to gradually become independent writers;
- Encouraging rhetorical awareness-raising by training students to notice and use the rhetoric patterns relevant to their disciplines.

Discussing the purposes of texts that GW curricula can target, Beale (1987) identifies (1) a deliberative or rhetorical purpose by which the writer tries to defend a point of

view regarding an issue; (2) a performative purpose whose aim is to promote the values of a specific group; (3) an informative purpose to deliver information about a topic; and (4) a reflective purpose whose objective is to share and reflect on life stories through poetry, novels, etc. Learners need to know the purpose / purposes of their writing community and then practice through models in order to produce effective and efficient texts. In a celebratory narrative about genre writing, Cooper (1999) recounts,

Fortunately knowledge about genres – about written discourse, our primary subject as English teachers – gave me new ways of thinking about my students’ struggles with writing. It changed the way I helped students shape their own projects. It changed the way I gave assignments and evaluated students’ works-in-progress. Because knowledge about genres also changed my ideas about the relation of reading to writing, it changed the way I organized my courses.

Central to Cooper’s account is that genre is an innovative and all-encompassing approach that positively impacts the learning, teaching, evaluation, and assessment of writing, and strongly emphasizes its interconnectedness with reading and the social context in which it is produced.

Of equal importance, genre-writing theory has made up for the inability of process and product writing approaches to consider the “ways meanings are socially constructed” and “the forces outside the individual which help guide purposes, establish relationships, and ultimately shape writing” (Hyland, 2003, p. 17-18). As such, Hyland adds, genre approaches have moved away “from a highly restricted view of human activity over-reliant on psychological factors, to a socially informed theory... grounded in research of texts and contexts” (p. 18). This is reflective of the claim that the learning of a skill is most effective when it takes place connectedly with the other skills, and within the range of the social and communicative context(s) in and for which it is learned. Writing, as such, should not be learnt separately from the other skills, notably reading. It is our conviction, accordingly, that reading is the feed of writing and that good writers are avid readers. However, for effective writing, genre would recommend reading texts that belongs to the genre community.

Last but not least, Swales (1990) emphasizes the importance of rhetorical instruction the genre approach provides which, he believes, is of similar value to the previous knowledge learners bring into the writing task. In other words, Rahman (2011) explains, this is “very beneficial because it brings together formal and functional properties of a language in writing instruction, and it acknowledges that there are strong association between them” (p. 6). Bhatia (1993) argues the fact that genre writing develops learners’ formal and structural awareness of their community’s writing is important because it enables them to understand why and how certain linguistic aspects are preferred in order to effectively achieve the targeted rhetorical outcomes.

Genre Writing Demerits

The literature identifies few limitations to EFL genre-based writing pedagogy among which one is of special importance. This relates to the learners’ passivity which originates from the limitation of their free expression because lessons tend to merely concentrate on the modeling of texts and the satisfying of readers’ expectations (Badger & White, 2000; Bawarshi, 2000; Swales, 2000). Such trepidation stems from the claim that “a genre can be a useful guideline or frame to the writers but also be an unwelcome tool of repression of creative thinking and expression” (Lee, 2013, p. 316).

However, a well-trained writing teacher can overcome this predicament by working out activities that engage learners in active negotiation and building of thought, adopting variety in terms of style, rhetoric patterns, and ways of thinking (Bakhtin, 1986). In fact, “all genre scholars acknowledge that the success of genre pedagogies is highly dependent on the professional knowledge of writing teachers” (Worden, 2018, p. 45). Also, researchers have “begun to explore how individuals are able to exploit genre options to create some personal wriggle-room and express a persona they feel comfortable with” (Hyland, 2015, p. 33). Then, “excluding genres from the classroom is not really an option, as they are the primary means through which humans communicate in writing” (Tardy, 2016, p. 129).

Genre, is “a term used for grouping texts together, representing how writers typically use language to respond to recurring situations” which “allows teachers to understand, and make explicit to students, the ways that texts can be written to achieve particular purposes” (Hyland, 2018, p. 2359). It can be pedagogically understood from the views of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), New Rhetoric (NR), English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and, to a lower degree, from the view of Critical Analysis (CA) (Hyon, 1996). To maintain relevance to the scope of the current study, the focus in discussing these perspectives is on their theoretical frameworks and their EFL pedagogical implications in the context of tertiary education.

English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

The primary objectives of this section are two-fold. One is to delve into the language theories that form the foundation of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) as a genre writing perspective. This exploration provides insight into the theoretical foundations that inform the approach’s application in language teaching-learning. The other goal is to critically elaborate on the practical measures involved in translating this perspective into EFL writing classroom practices. By emphasizing the context of tertiary education, it becomes possible to assess the effectiveness and challenges of implementing genre writing pedagogy with the Moroccan university EFL context. Also, addressing both theoretical frameworks and practical considerations provides a comprehensive understanding of the role of ESP in enhancing the teaching-learning of writing within tertiary EFL contexts.

Methodology

Research Instrument

Interviews

The current study makes use of a one-to-one semi-structured interview to collect qualitative data about the insights of University Moroccan EFL professors with regards to the opportunities and challenges relating to the teaching-learning of writing from the perspective of genre writing pedagogy. The decision to conduct semi-structured interviews stems from their flexibility in accommodating various themes that researchers may not anticipate during the interview preparation (Adams, 2015). Adams explains, Semi-structured interviews “can meander around the topics on the agenda-rather than adhering slavishly to verbatim questions...and may delve into totally unforeseen issues” (p.493). Additionally, they offer flexibility in phrasing and wording questions as needed (Berg, 2009). For these reasons, the current study has conducted semi-structured interviews with 16 university Moroccan EFL professors, who have taught writing at university.

The interview comprises various components. First, it gathers information about the interviewee's academic background and professional experience to ensure their relevance to the interview's objectives. Second, it evaluates the broader significance of writing in higher education. Third, it delves into genre writing, focusing on questions directly related to the teaching and learning of writing using genre pedagogy. Fourth, it explores the effectiveness of genre writing pedagogy in enhancing the writing skills of Moroccan university students. Fifth, it addresses the challenges and limitations that may be encountered in teaching and learning genre writing pedagogy. Sixth, it seeks the interviewees' suggestions for practical measures to overcome these challenges, if any. Seventh, it discusses future implications and recommendations pertaining to genre writing pedagogy.

Finally, the interview provides a summary of the key insights, perspectives, and recommendations shared during the interview. It then expresses the due gratitude for the valuable contributions of the professors for helping to explore the teaching of writing in EFL departments at Moroccan universities from the perspective of GWP.

Sampling

University Moroccan professors served as informants for the interviews conducted in the current study. These professors possess extensive experience in teaching writing, having worked as researchers, professors, or both. The table below presents information regarding each of the interviewed professors.

Name	Gender	Experience / Years	University
T.K.	Male	15	Mohamed V University, Rabat
H.A.	Female	7	Mohamed V University, Rabat
A.D.	Male	20	Hassan I University, Settat
A.A.	Male	15	Mohamed V University, Rabat
T.B.	Male	5	Ibn Zohr University, Agadir
H.S.	Male	7	Moulay Ismail University, Meknes
A.A.	Female	10	Moulay Ismail University, Meknes
O.N.	Male	25	Mohamed V University, Rabat
T.K.	Female	22	Mohamed V University, Rabat
A.F.	Male	5	Abdelmalek Esaadi University, Marrakech
F.A.	Female	17	Mohamed V University, Rabat
Y.E.	Female	10	Ibn Zohr University, Agadir
M.B.	Male	7	Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra
K.H.	Female	13	Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra
J.A.	Male	4	Mohamed V University, Rabat
O.B.	Male	5	Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez

Figure 2. Gender and Experience of Interviewed Professors

Sampling Procedures

The interview sampling process for university Moroccan professors involves a combination of convenience and purposive techniques. As mentioned above, convenience sampling is instrumental in selecting a number of interviewees that is critical for the validity of the study's findings. These participants, possessing significant expertise in teaching and learning within EFL departments at Moroccan universities, have been crucial for providing insightful perspectives. Initially, contact was established with forty potential professors through various communication channels

including phone calls, WhatsApp messages, emails, and face-to-face interactions. Nevertheless, ultimately, only sixteen professors demonstrated both availability and willingness to participate in the interviews.

The sixteen participants, however, were deemed to be enough to offer valuable insights into the dynamics of writing teaching-learning in the Moroccan higher education context, since 12 interviewees from a homogenous community are enough to attain saturation (Guest et al., 2006). The perspectives of the participants have actually enriched the study's findings, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the status of genre writing pedagogy at EFL departments in Moroccan universities.

Data Collection Procedures

A total of 18 EFL university professors from Morocco participated as interview informants. Initially, the researcher established contact and received confirmation from 42 professors to participate in the interview. However, due to professional constraints, only 18 were able to take part (two participants requested to withdraw from the interview). The interviews were conducted both face-to-face with six professors and via Google Meet with the remaining ten.

The interview process commenced with a piloting phase where the questions were tested for relevance and operationality. One professor and a PhD graduate with 18 years of experience in EFL teaching, including 5 years at the university level, participated in this pilot phase. Participants involved in the piloting stage were subsequently excluded from the analyzed data to ensure trustworthiness.

Following the piloting phase, the researcher arranged meetings or telephone calls with participants to agree on the mode and timing of the interview. For those who were not reachable, contact was made via email for the same purposes. Subsequently, an email was sent to all participants informing them about the general aims of the research and the specific objectives of the interview. The average duration of each interview was approximately 15 minutes. Then, all interviews were recorded and transcribed using the Otter.ai platform.

Interviews with university Moroccan Professors are delivered to explore the insights they have about teaching-learning writing at EFL departments from the perspective of genre writing pedagogy. Due to confidentiality concerns, the study does not reveal information about the informants, especially their names and the universities where they teach. All interviews were transcribed using Otter.ai before they were studied using an inductive thematic content analysis, whose objective was to identify patterns that were common across the responses of the informants. After preparing transcript files, the researcher and two assistants read the interviews and made a list of themes. Based on the findings, the researcher annotated the transcripts and assigned codes to ideas belonging to each of the emerging themes. Following this stage was data conceptualization whereby categories and subcategories were created based on the relevance of the codes to the objective of the study. After, the themes were segmented from the most important to the least important. Finally, the findings were summarized in relevance to themes of value to the teaching of Genre writing to Moroccan EFL MA applied linguistics students.

Findings and Discussions

Significance of Genre Writing

The responses regarding the significance of genre writing within applied linguistics show a high acknowledgment of its pivotal role amongst university professors. 10 of the 16 (62.5%) interviewees emphasize genre writing as a crucial skill fostering effective, not only writing, but also communication skills within the specific context of applied linguistics. A professor, with 7 years of university teaching experience, sees “genre writing as **an important skill** that helps students **communicate effectively** within the specific context of applied linguistics, which enhances their **academic and professional** development.” Another, with 5 year-experience, supports this view saying, “genre writing serves as **a bridge between theoretical knowledge** and **practical application** that prepares students for the demands of **real-world linguistic research** and **communication.**” A third testimony provides, teaching students genre writing “not only refines students’ writing abilities but also nurtures **a deeper understanding** of the unique **conventions** within the field of applied linguistics.” Other supportive responses view genre writing as an empowering tool, academic identity, and a valid way to refine students applied linguistics writing style. It is worth to mention that 6 of the professors who believe genre writing is an essential component to enable students to write effectively confirm a parallel need for trained teachers, well developed syllabi, rich material, and a full engagement of the students.

The literature backs the testimonies of the professors who think genre writing is an essential component university students need to achieve the quality writing skills required for success at and beyond university. For instance, Far and Mitchell (2020) have found, “Genre-Based Approach, with its focus on better genre characteristics identification along with improved teaching and learning methodology, combining elements of structure, language, rhetoric, and cultural contextualization, gives more rapid results, and leads to better and more confident writers, as well as better syllabus development.” These authors argue the learning of genre writing is effective in quickening students learning of writing; at the same, they, like Moroccan university professors, emphasize the need for appropriate teaching-learning contexts.

Four interviewees, however, have expressed some doubt with regards to the extent to which focusing on applied linguistic genre writing would positively benefit students’ writing. One of them, with a 15-year university teaching experience, says, “I think genre writing is **a mere formality**; its impact on practical language use can be **limited.**” Supporting this testimony is another interviewee’s claim that provides, “teaching genre writing might improve certain aspects but **may not be the key to overall writing quality.**” One other professor indicates, limiting the teaching of writing to students’ discipline will cause “students to get too focused on **rigid conventions** and may **lose creativity** in their writing.”

Finally, two professors have chosen not to have a say about the topic, particularly because they have never taught using genre writing pedagogy and thus cannot judge how effective such an endeavor can be in enabling students from the quality writing skills they need to succeed as students and as researchers.

Teaching Approaches and Strategies

The professors’ responses to the question about the strategies and approaches they would propose to teach university applied linguistics students’ genre writing reveal their high sense of awareness of teaching practices in general and the teaching of

writing in particular. A recurrent response mentioned by eight of the interviews emphasizes “**peer collaboration**” and “**appropriate feedback**” as key strategies to help students develop their writing skills. These according to an interviewee provide “a **supportive and anxiety free** environment where students can refine their genre-specific writing skills **depending on themselves** and within **the guidance of the professor.**” One professor recommends “**Scaffolded assignments**, meaning starting with simpler components and gradually progressing to **more complex** ones...can be **successful** in building students’ **confidence** in applying genre writing conventions.” Another interesting response highlights the incorporation of “**reflective exercises** that have students **reflect on their own writing** alone or in groups in relation to genre conventions. This encourages **metacognition and self-awareness** in students’ writing processes.” Of equal importance is a testament of a professor, which provides “the establishment of a clear connection between genre writing and future professional applications within applied linguistics motivates students to view genre writing as a valuable skill beyond the academic setting.” Then, almost all the interviewees have emphasized learning through models. This implies that teachers should provide sample applied linguistics texts, ensuring that students understand their lexico-grammar and rhetorical components before expecting them to produce similar written texts.

These views seem to be highly grounded in the literature, and as said earlier, reveal Moroccan university professors’ awareness of how to teach writing effectively, be it through the employment of process writing, product writing, or genre writing. For instance, the emphasis on group work and peer work learning modes is highly supported by the communicative approach, the constructive approach, and the discovery approach to learning a foreign language. However, the interviewed professors reveal there are a number of challenges that hinder the application of these teaching methods in Moroccan universities (these are going to be discussed later in this section).

Genre Writing Conventions

Questions related to what specific genre writing conventions the professors consider particularly important for students to learn within the applied linguistics context have yielded a number of interesting answers. On top of these are the rhetorical features. Nine of the sixteen interviewed professors have highlighted the need for students to be aware of the rhetorical features they need to abide by while writing, for instance, the abstract, introduction, and discussion of their dissertations. An interesting response says, “Absolutely, understanding **rhetorical moves** is **crucial** for applied linguistics students to write effectively. Rhetorical moves help them **structure their writing**, convey their ideas **persuasively**, and **align with the conventions of academic discourse** in the field. It’s like having a **roadmap** for producing coherent, effective written texts in applied linguistics.” When asked about the importance of applied linguistics lexico-grammar patterns, a respondent interestingly comments, “Oh, totally! Knowing those applied linguistics lexico-grammar patterns is like having **the magic stick for good writing**. It’s all about using **the right words and grammar in a way that clicks with the language of applied linguistics**. So, yeah, **super important** for writing dissertations and all other texts, I think!” Two professors have highlighted the importance of learning **citation and referencing conventions**. One of them points out, “You know, in the world of applied linguistics and university writing in general, students better write citation and referencing rules. It’s like the golden ticket to navigate through the academic discourse universe.” The same professor has complained about students not being well knowledgeable about these

features, which might be according to him “the result of a lack of training or maybe a lack of interest from the part of the students.”

Many studies Support the need for a university syllabus that teaches students the genre writing conventions highlighted by the interviewed professors. Of these studies, one by María Martínez-Lirola (2015) proves the exposure of students to model texts with a focus on the lexico-grammar writing conventions improves their ability to produce written texts with a quality that gain them access to their writing communities, at the academic and professional levels (Bawarshi, 2010). Another study by Saidi and Talbi (2022) highlights the importance of students learning rhetorical conventions that align with the expectations of their discourse community. The study concludes by emphasizing the need to train professors in writing abstracts, as it is essential for them to be qualified to instruct their students to effectively produce their own texts. Finally, Martin and Burgess (2024) accentuate the importance of writers' awareness of rhetorical moves in crafting quality applied linguistics texts. They recommend integrating such knowledge into pedagogical contexts, especially ones concerning the teaching of English as a foreign language.

In conclusion, the findings strongly advocate for the inclusion of applied linguistics genre writing conventions in university syllabi. The professors' testimonials, as summarized above, and previous studies on the topic provide compelling justification for this necessity.

Challenges and Observations

The positive perception of conducting a university program to teach genre writing by the interviewees brings forth several challenges that they believe may impact the accurate implementation of such a program.

According to one of the testaments, “Understanding genre conventions in the context of applied linguistics may be **challenging**, as **students might not have prior exposure to these specific writing norms.**” In fact, the delayed specialization of EFL students in Moroccan universities, particularly in applied linguistics, poses a significant challenge. The writing and composition training they receive earlier in their academic journey may not align with the specific discourse communities they eventually enter. This misalignment can have several implications for them to learn applied linguistics genre writing. Likewise, an interviewee testifies, “the writing skills acquired in **general education** may not be easily **tailored** to the **specialized discourse** of applied linguistics.” Similarly, a professor states, “without early exposure to applied linguistics genres, students may lack awareness of the rhetorical and stylistic features crucial for successful communication within the field.”

Because nearly 65% of the interviewees have stressed the challenge posed by delayed specialization in impeding students' mastery of applied linguistics genre writing, the question of whether specialization should be determined earlier gains particular significance. Early specialization may equip students with the necessary applied linguistics rhetorical and linguistically functional input to be able to produce quality writing. Ten professors have agreed this should certainly be the case, especially that, as one professor says, “early specialization means students would be exposed to language material that belongs to one discipline, be it linguistics, applied linguistics or literature. As a result, the students would be unconsciously prepared to produce language content similar to what their professors expose them to.” However, the same professor interjects, “I still believe if a student is good at writing about general topics, he or she will be good at writing in applied linguistics although they may need to have some

aware training on how to write in their disciplines, especially when it comes to rhetorical moves, style, etc.”

Due and appropriate feedback is another challenge some interviewees have underscored. One of them states, “I believe it **necessary for professors to share their feedback** about what a student writes, and this should be **on a continuous basis**. **Unfortunately**, the number of students is most of the time, except for graduate levels, is too high and it is impossible to provide feedback for every student. It’s too much to read let’s say paragraphs of 200 students or more, let alone essays. So, professors usually provide students with the necessary tools to write well, and it is up to the them to complement or better yet handle the practice and feedback part. I share with them strategies to work on their writing on their own, in pairs, in groups, reading texts in applied linguistics... I am sure a few of them do with these recommendations but I think many others don’t.” Another professor supports this claim saying, “it is more time consuming to provide personalized feedback that caters to the weaknesses of each student.”

Other challenges include “the lack of applied linguistics genre writing syllabi”, “low interest of students in writing compared to especially speaking”, and issues in producing high quality written texts in general.

Finally, only two professors confirm that they have observed improvements in their students’ applied linguistics writing conventions after using genre writing pedagogy in their teaching. They simultaneously mentioned that their implementation of genre pedagogy to teach writing was confined to specific sessions within their writing and/or composition courses. The other professors expressed an inability to judge, citing their lack of experience in teaching writing using genre writing pedagogy.

University Support and Integration

This part aims at identifying how university programs can better support both professors and students in integrating genre writing effectively into the curriculum. A recurrent response provides there is some need for the development of professors’ knowledge and understanding of genre writing in applied linguistics as well as in other specialties. For instance, a professor declares that “if we agree that the teaching of genre writing is necessary at university – I am saying if we agree- then we have to provide professional development for professors to enhance their own understanding of genre writing by, maybe, organizing genre writing workshops or courses, encouraging research about the topic both by professors and students.”

Another interviewee proposes “establishing writing centers and clubs at university to support the learning of writing depending on the needs of the students and if that is learning how to write in applied linguistics why not establishing it. This would give the students the opportunity they need to explore and develop their skills free from the stress and anxiety of the classroom, midterms, finals...It is also an opportunity for those who are interested in writing to meet and discuss what and how to improve their skills. We unfortunately and to my knowledge lack this in our universities here in Morocco. I think it’s worth it.” Supporting this proposition is a testament by a professor who thinks “building a community of practice dedicated to genre writing within applied linguistics can encourage networking and the exchange of ideas, ultimately enriching the overall teaching and learning experience.”

Likewise, the use of information communication technology (ICT) has been frequently recommended by the interviewed professors as a valuable component for teaching genre writing. For instance, a professor recommends “creating an online repository of

resources, including best practices, case studies, and successful examples of genre writing integration, would provide a readily accessible reference for both professors and students.” She adds, “it is time students were empowered and why not given some part of the responsibility of their learning by making them in charge of these online platforms. Of course, the guidance of professors should always be there in order to make sure the system is well operated and the objective are still attained.” One other interviewee responds, “considering the technological advancements, developing digital tools or platforms specifically designed for teaching and learning genre writing could enhance accessibility and engagement – I mean accessibility to the database and engagement in the learning process.”

A quite interesting response highlights the need for “collaboration amongst departments an why not universities in terms of the programs they offer, including genre writing syllabi. As a result, he adds, “professors and students would have access to additional assistance and resources dedicated to genre writing.” Interestingly, this proposition envisions a supportive environment where professors and students can engage with resources and assistance specifically designed to genre writing teaching and learning. Simultaneously, the interdisciplinary collaboration aims to enhance the overall learning experience and facilitate access to valuable support in developing genre writing skills amongst learners as students and as researchers.

Designing GW Lessons for Moroccan EFL Context

Moroccan university professors proposed interesting measures for the design of GW lessons tailored to the needs and challenges of the Moroccan EFL context. According to five interviewed professors, the first measure relates to the need to incorporate culturally relevant examples and materials, which integrate local contexts and language features into the lessons. To elaborate on this, one professor recommended designing lessons with language and content that relate to the Moroccan context. For her, “students would develop a sense of appreciation for Moroccan culture when exploring applied linguistics written by Moroccans or related to Morocco. This could also teach students the conventions of writing genres and, at the same time, motivate them to join the Moroccan writing community as future authors.”

The second important measure identified in the interviews was the need for lessons based on scaffolding. Almost half of the interviewed professors claimed that through gradually increasing the complexity of writing assignments and consistently providing necessary support, students can build their writing skills. One professor commented, “this approach ensures that all students are able to make progress in their writing abilities, despite the difficulty of applying it with some groups due to the large number of students.”

The third measure emphasized by the interviewed professors is explicit instruction. They claim that by teaching students how to identify and analyze different genres, as well as the purposes and conventions associated with each genre, students can become more proficient writers. This includes providing opportunities for students to practice writing in various genres and receive feedback on their work. One professor stated, “This measure not only raises students’ awareness of the genre conventions relevant to their writing communities but also develops their critical thinking at a time when memorization is too old and useless in teaching.”

Similarly, the interviews revealed the enthusiasm of Moroccan university professors for teaching writing using GWP. However, they also expressed concerns about the existing challenges that could diminish the effectiveness of any teaching approach.

Among these challenges, they mentioned large class sizes, insufficient access to information and communication technology, and a lack of academic training for both professors and students.

Conclusion

The professors' responses provide valuable insights into the challenges and strategies associated with teaching EFL genre writing in applied linguistics at the university level. It is evident that there is a strong awareness among these educators regarding the significance of genre writing in enhancing students', communication in general and writing in particular, skills within the specific context of applied linguistics. The emphasis on peer collaboration, feedback, and the use of models emphasizes the practical approaches considered effective in teaching genre writing.

Furthermore, the professors acknowledge the importance of integrating genre writing seamlessly into the curriculum, balancing it with other aspects of applied linguistics education. Their suggestions for effective teaching strategies, such as using real-world examples, scaffolded assignments, and reflective exercises, reveal a commitment to fostering students' engagement with genre writing conventions.

The professors' observations regarding challenges, including students' struggles with genre-specific conventions and the need for early specialization in applied linguistics, highlight areas for improvement in curriculum design and pedagogical approaches. The mentioning of information communication technology as a teaching tool indicates a recognition of the evolving role of technology in enhancing genre writing instruction, especially in contexts where these technologies are available for both professors and students.

In general, the professors' responses collectively highlight the importance of recognizing and addressing the specific writing needs of students studying applied linguistics in Morocco. Their insights pave the way for refining or implementing pedagogical practices, boosting interdisciplinary collaborations, and using technology to create a more supportive and effective learning environment for genre writing within the applied linguistics discipline at Moroccan universities.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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